

"ECONOMIC MECHANISM FOR IMPLEMENTING MODERN AGROTECHNOLOGY IN COTTON FARMING AND ENSURING ECOLOGICAL BALANCE"

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In the cotton industry, increasing the volume of production and improving its quality are largely dependent on the characteristics of cotton varieties. Quality agronomic practices carried out in cotton fields and the yield indicators determined by the genetic potential of cotton varieties manifest themselves through these measures. Any newly created variety, which has relatively high agricultural and economic indicators, will only fully realize its potential when proper agronomic practices and effective agrotechnologies are implemented.

A variety that is capable of producing quality products that meet market demand and is adapted to the local conditions of the region will only show expected results if quality seeds are used and agronomic measures are carried out timely and effectively. Therefore, the future of cotton growing is also dependent on the introduction of new agrotechnologies.

Achieving high yields, improving fiber quality, and reducing production costs in cotton growing is impossible without the implementation of resource-saving and efficient agrotechnologies. Taking into account the market demand for cotton products and the differences in climate change in cotton-growing regions (water scarcity, early autumn cold, and rain), the development of cotton varieties and the changes in cotton cultivation agrotechnics will have a significant impact.

Currently, the following new agrotechnologies are considered relevant in the cotton industry:

- Changes in irrigation systems:
 - o Due to increasing water scarcity, the use of drip irrigation, sprinkler irrigation, mulched irrigation, stratified irrigation according to the depth of water layers, irrigation through flexible pipes, and inter-row irrigation systems.
- Changes in soil treatment:
 - o Minimal soil cultivation in cotton fields, selecting the depth of plowing based on the characteristics of the region, planting seeds under plastic film, and drastically reducing the number of soil treatments.
- Changes in fertilization and mineral fertilizer ratios:

o Reducing the consumption of mineral fertilizers based on the use of local fertilizers, adjusting the ratio of mineral fertilizers (NPK) in layers, and utilizing siderate crops.

- Increasing the use of biological methods in the fight against weeds, cotton diseases, and pests, as well as in defoliation.

- Changes in the cotton vegetation period:

- o Considering new technologies for one-time harvesting, defoliation, and boll-opening.

The use of ecological agrotechnical methods in cotton growing is a complex process, as it is directly related to the cotton industry's significance, which plays a notable role in environmental issues, and also to cotton farmers' activities, where there is little material incentive for environmental protection.

To resolve this issue, it is necessary to implement a mechanism (a material incentive mechanism) to encourage cotton-growing farms to apply environmentally less harmful agrotechnologies in cotton growing, based on the principles of private ownership and free entrepreneurship.

Secondly, an effective and simple method must be developed for monitoring the environmental pollution process by state authorities and the public.

When addressing environmental issues related to the development of the cotton sector, it is essential to pay attention to the following aspects when evaluating the ecological safety of new agrotechnical methods:

- Cotton growing farm characteristics: Soil composition, fertility, and meliorative condition of cotton fields, water supply level, and depth of irrigation water.

- Economic efficiency of cotton production and the degree of resource expenditure recovery.

- Population density in cotton-growing regions, its impact on employment in the cotton sector, and the share of agricultural income in household budgets.

- The compatibility of existing machinery with cotton cultivation technology and the level of material-technical resources supply.

- The level of introducing crop rotation systems and its effect on soil fertility in cotton-growing fields.

- The degree of harm of food products (cotton oil) and animal feed (cake, meal, and hulls) produced from cotton processing for both human and animal consumption.

- The impact of existing agrotechnical practices on the ecological balance in the region.

Based on the above scientific and practical conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. In the cotton sector, it is necessary to take into account the meliorative condition of the land and the level of water usage when implementing agrotechnical measures.

2. In the cotton sector, to reduce the impact on the ecological balance of the region, it is necessary to use more organic fertilizers when applying agrotechnical measures.

References:

1. Khushmatov N., Problems of raw cotton production in the republic: Collection of Scientific Works of the Uzbekistan Scientific Research Institute of Textile and Light Industry (UzBIITI). – Tashkent, 2002. - p. 31.
2. Beknazarov U.F., Myrzaev B.J. Development of the cotton industry and the integration of the ecological advisory system. – Tashkent, UzBIITI, 2007, - pp. 57-58.
3. Beknazarov U., Fayzulloyeva T. Ecological balance // Agriculture of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent, 2007. - No. 6, p. 19.
4. Results of the author's scientific and practical research.

